

LINGUOPRAGMATIC STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Annotation: The main purpose of the article is to define and explain the meaning of this term, and why we need it. The research explored comparative method in both finding the theory and suitable examples. The finding of the research shows the impact of pragmatics in real life conversation. While socializing people really need pragmatic meaning for understanding speaker's attitude, feeling and thoughts. Theoretical contributions and practical implications are presented by phraseological units, idioms and authentic dialogues, and drew a conclusion, opposite meaning of semantics argued as pragmatics.

Keywords: simple structured units, symbolic meaning, pragmema, informema, anthropocentric, speech portrait of a person, pragmatic failure.

INTRODUCTION

Everyone wants his speech to be rich, emotional and expressive. One of the main ways to achieve this is a reasonable use of different phraseological expressions, idioms, proverbs, sayings, colorful expressions.

The founder of the theory of phraseology is a Swiss linguist Charles Bally. Bally was the first who systematized the combination of the words in his books "Studies of the Stylistics" and "French Stylistics". Ch. Bally explored the sphere of linguistics and phraseology in the French language, however, his attempt to systematize and classify phraseological units led to the series of other studies in the phraseological sphere in other languages, including English¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methods of investigation that are used in this work are linguopragmatical conceptual analysis including cognitive mapping and conceptual blending. Methodological basis of the given article is works of such scholars as G. Lakoff and M. Johnson, Kubryakova, V. Z. Demyankov; Chudinov, Kunin and many others. Phraseological units are considerable parts of any language. Therefore, they are studied by plenty of scholars. For example, Russian scholars Vinogradov, A.I. Smidnitoski, H. N. Asomova and Uzbek scholars Sh. Rahmatullayev, A. E. Mamatov, B. Yo'ldoshev conducted a research on this sphere of linguistics². Their works and researches play significant role in the

¹ Ariel, M. (2010). Research survey in linguistics. Cambridge University Press.

² Hiraga, M.K., & Fujii (2013). L2 Pragmatics in Academic Discourse: A Case Study of Tutorials in Britain. Tutorials in Britain.

development of phraseology. Even nowadays, this field of linguistics attracts great many of scholars' attention. A.B. Pittman defines phraseological units in his works as a group of words in a fixed order that is different from the meaning of each word understood on its own (Urantaeva N, 2017). In fact, idioms can never be translated into another language word for word. Otherwise, they lose their semantic meaning. For instance, if we translate the idiom "Lend an ear" into Uzbek word by word, it means "qulog'ini qarzga bermoq". Because, the word "lend" means to let someone borrow something that belongs to you for a short time. However, in this work you can see this kind of phraseological units with its equivalents in Uzbek language³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linguistic pragmatics do not have a clear form. It includes a set of issues related to the speaker and the listener, their interaction in the speech process. Linguistic pragmatism includes a realistic expression of social activity. Uzbek linguistics has conducted some research on the pragmatic aspects, the relationship between the speaker and the listener, the interaction of participants in the speech act, and their influence on ethical emotions. The problems of linguistic pragmatics does not have their own interpretation. As a part of Pragmatics and a part of the linguistic science, the word pragmaling seems to be a natural thing to say about the category of units.

There are two pragmalingvistic units:

1. Informema.
2. Pragmema.

As an example: "wallflower" translating word by word the meaning is flower is hung on the wall – informema.

Girl who was not invited to dance (in a party)- pragmema.

Pragmalingvistic units are directly affected by language units and functional language areas. The pragmats come into opposition with the information-gathering function. Pragmembers are always pragmatic information carriers.

The phraseological idioms are determined by social and political aspects, traditions, customs, cultural values which create similar thematic domains in all investigated languages. The cultural concepts in the research will be described within a broader anthropocentric paradigm since it includes the cultural dimension; and its central assumption is that every language, especially its figurative meanings is connected with the reflection of the world-view shared by the linguistic knowledge about the reality. Cultural concepts in anthropocentric phraseology of the proposed research are abstract notions such as, for instance,

³ Ashurova, D.U. (2012). Text of linguistics. Tashkent: "Tashakkur qanoti".

intellectual ability, emotional and expressive aspects, empathy and other positive traits of human nature as well as bad sides of human nature, which construct the world-picture in a culturally specific way. Both concepts proper and sub-concepts are involved. It is noteworthy indeed that “their specificity is implemented mostly at the cognitive, not the semantic level because cultural background refers to information that is most difficult to formalize, as it is connected with semantics in a very indirect and still unexplored way” as, for instance, in the paradigm the traits of character with the positive meaning in the sub-concept smart, capable: Uzbek.: kallabor¹) someone is very smart, capable⁴; 2) to do something after proper consideration: Mening ham kalam bor!

CONCLUSION

To conclude, we admit that, in many cases, we deal with similar logical and semantic patterns in all investigated languages because of the existence of the same human universal spirit, of a resembling ontological experience, of a common European identity. We could also assert, on the basis of the previously analyzed descriptive material, that there are unique phraseological units in the culture and mentality of each community, determined by different economic, social, historical and psychological aspects. Since phraseology in comparative linguo-cultural studies is still relatively young field of research, much more corpora are necessary to learn and understand the national spirit of the certain ethnic group through cultural concepts.

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